

FEATURES OF THE HOT POTATOES PROGRAM

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Abstract: In this article, you will get acquainted with the capabilities of the Hot Potatoes program, its application area, its options, file extensions.

Keywords: Internet Explorer, JMix, JQuiz, JCloze, JMatch AutoPlay, Ispring.

Hot Potatoes is an instrumental shell program designed for teachers to prepare independent interactive assignments. While working with this program, the user is not required to know the programming language.

With the help of the program, you can prepare text, graphic and audio-video tasks in 10 different languages.

One of the main features of the program is that the created tasks are saved in the form of a standard web page. Students do not need Hot Potatoes for this. All they need is a web browser (for example, Internet Explorer). This program is only needed by teachers to create and edit their assignments. This program is widely used around the world. This program was created in 1997-2003 at the Information Technology Center of the University of Victoria, Canada. (<http://web.uvic.ca/hcmc>).

Authors: Stewart Arneil, Martin Holmes, Hilary Street

The main blocks of the program

Tasks are created using the following 6 blocks of the program (each block is considered as an independent program):

1. Correct the JMix sequence.
2. JQuiz Quiz questions have multiple choice answers.
3. JCloze to fill in the omitted word.
4. JCross Crossword.
5. Set JMatch Compatibility.
6. JMasher. The test created in all sections compiles crosswords into a single web page.

The results of tasks are evaluated in percentages. Incorrect attempts will decrease the percentage of grade results. In the 6 th version of the program, an additional blog JMasher was

added, which performs the task of summarizing tasks created in other blocks of the program.

After that, all files are copied to the folder of the program.

Let's consider each of the above blocks with examples.

1. JQuiz is designed to create a variety of tests. When we run it, the following window will appear:

This window consists of file, edit, install, manage, search, select and help menus, toolbar and workspace.

The name of the subject is written in the first line of the workspace, and questions are written in the next line. Answers are written in the Otvety column, comments are written in the Kommertarii column, verno boxes are marked for the correct answer in the Nastroyki column. For example:

To the second and subsequent questions, we add the 2nd, 3rd and subsequent questions from paragraph B with the help of a slider. Through the Vid webstranitsy item of the program's Vybor menu or the icon of the window, we create the configuration parameters of the file we are saving as a web page.

After starting the Vid webstranitsy section, the following window will appear:

Through the items in this window, we adjust the specified parameters of our test. To save the generated file, we use items such as Sochranit, Sochranit kak of the file menu. To save our file as a web page, we use the icon on the toolbar.

For example:

It is ready by pressing the button to view the browser, we can see the text in the browser

2. Tests created in JMix are executed by correctly placing a certain sequence. Here, the sequence of words is entered in the left field (Osnovnoe predlozhenie) one by one, in ascending or descending order.

We can also create a project created in this program and test it in two different ways. The test created by pressinF6 key is as follows:

Here, the left mouse button is clicked on the words below in sequence, whichever word is selected, the next word will be created in the sequence above.

In the second view, the words are placed and arranged in sequence using the mouse Drag&Drop method.

To translate the English words here or write other words instead, you can change it from the Vybor menu in the Vid webstranitsy section.

3. JClose - allows you to fill in omitted words in the text.

Run Hot Potatoes, select JCloze from the window that appears, or we can also select JCloze from the Potatoes menu.

As a result, the following window will appear:

Enter the name of the task you want to create in the "Imya" line: (M: Find the omitted words in the text.). We write some text in the empty space below it. For example, "The smallest unit of measurement of information is a bit" Then select the word "bit" and click the "Probe" button located below, and the following window will appear as a result.

Then we can describe it through the "opredelenie" clause, that is, in order to help the student, even if we omit it, it will not be considered a deficiency. In addition, we can add alternative answers and click OK. Then the following window will appear on the screen. Now let's look at the settings of the task we created so that we can generate the result in the browser.

After pressing the specified buttons, the following windows will appear:

After completing the settings, we perform the following actions.

We name the task and save it.

If you can do the tasks correctly, the result should be as follows.

In conclusion, the information provided in this article incorporates theoretical knowledge, programs that create electronic learning resources, multimedia technologies and their fields of application. Implementation of the goal of educational reforms depends on a number of important factors. Among them, there are such complex problems that it is impossible to talk about the effect of fundamental changes without successfully solving these problems. The process of solving such problems is the development of the electronic education system and the creation of electronic information resources among the knowledge provided on the basis of new pedagogical technologies.

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